
GHG EMISSIONS INVENTORY OF MEDITERRANEAN SMALL-SCALE FISHERIES

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ABSTRACT

Small-scale fisheries (SSF) are a key socio-economic component of Mediterranean coastal communities, yet their contribution to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions remains poorly documented. This report presents the first coordinated inventory of CO₂ emissions from Mediterranean SSF developed within the WWF “Transforming Small-Scale Fisheries in the Mediterranean – Phase II” project. Pilot sites in Italy, Croatia, Türkiye, and Tunisia were selected to represent different environmental, operational, and socio-economic contexts.

Data collection combined standardized questionnaires and geospatial tracking of selected vessels to estimate and validate fuel consumption. CO₂ emissions were calculated following a Tier 1 IPCC-based methodology using fuel-specific emission factors for diesel and gasoline engines. Emission intensity was evaluated both per unit of landed biomass and per unit of economic value.

Results revealed strong variability among sites, reflecting differences in vessel characteristics, fishing practices, target species, and spatial distribution of fishing effort. Croatian sites generally showed lower emission intensities, while Tunisian fisheries exhibited considerably higher values. A common trend observed across several pilot areas was the lower emission intensity associated with the main commercial target species, suggesting that targeting efficiency may contribute to reducing the carbon footprint of artisanal fisheries.

Despite some methodological limitations and uneven data coverage among pilot sites, the integration of survey and tracking data proved effective in establishing regional emission baselines. The findings highlight the need for harmonized monitoring protocols and context-specific mitigation strategies to support sustainable fisheries management and future climate-oriented policies for the Mediterranean SSF sector.

INTRODUCTION

Small-Scale Fisheries (SSF) play a vital socio-economic role in the Mediterranean region, yet they are increasingly challenged by environmental and economic pressures (1). Fishing activities contribute to greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions primarily through fossil fuel combustion (2,3), and in turn are impacted by climate change, which alters ecosystems, species distributions, and fishing patterns (4).

Recognizing the dual need to mitigate emissions and adapt to changing conditions, the WWF Mediterranean Programme launched the *Transforming Small-Scale Fisheries in the Mediterranean* project. The second phase of this initiative has focused specifically on establishing the first regional inventory of CO₂ emissions from SSF, aiming to create a robust baseline for future mitigation strategies.

Building on previous efforts (5), this report expands the scope of CO₂ emission monitoring by including pilot sites from four countries (Figure 1): Italy (Veneto, Friuli Venezia Giulia, and Sicily), Croatia (Velebit Channel and Vis Archipelago), Türkiye (Mordoğan), and Tunisia (Gulf of Gabes). Although Spain (Catalunya and Balearic Islands) was initially included in the project framework, data from Spanish sites were eventually unavailable and thus excluded from the analysis.

The objective of this report is to quantify CO₂ emissions generated by SSF activities in the selected pilot sites, estimate seasonal variations, and assess emission intensity both per unit of catch and per economic value.

Figure 1. Pilot sites involved in the SSF CO₂ monitoring effort, throughout the Mediterranean, within the SSF2 Project.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 STUDY AREA AND FLEET CHARACTERIZATION

Data was collected from a network of pilot sites representing a diversity of Mediterranean coastal ecosystems and small-scale fishing practices.

Small-scale coastal fisheries are defined under Regulation (EU) No 508/2014 as fishing activities carried out by vessels below 12 m in length overall (LOA) that do not operate towed gears. In practical terms, this segment mainly includes artisanal and coastal fleets using small vessels and traditional, mostly passive fishing gears, together with some small purse seine operations. These activities are generally conducted close to shore, often within a few nautical miles from the coast, and are typically organised as single-day fishing trips.

Adriatic Sea

The Adriatic Sea is a semi-enclosed basin oriented along a northwest–southeast axis, covering approximately 140,000 km². It is about 800 km long and 150–200 km wide. Overall, it is relatively shallow, although depth increases progressively from north to south. The basin is commonly divided into three sub-basins, each characterized by distinct physical, biological, and geomorphological features (6,7).

According to the FAO-GFCM geographical subdivision of the Mediterranean, GSA17 includes the northern and central Adriatic sub-basins. The northern Adriatic is particularly shallow, with average depths of about 30–35 m, whereas the central Adriatic reaches greater depths, generally around 130–150 m and up to approximately 270 m in the Pomo/Jabuka Pit. This area is among the most heavily exploited fishing grounds in the Mediterranean, particularly in relation to trawling pressure (8,9).

Italy

The Italian pilot sites included Veneto (Caorle and Chioggia), Friuli Venezia Giulia (Marano Lagunare), and Sicily (Gulf of Patti).

- ***Friuli-Venezia Giulia (Marano Lagunare):***

The small-scale fishing fleet of Marano Lagunare operates primarily within the lagoon and adjacent coastal areas. The fleet consists mainly of small diesel-powered vessels, with the majority using gillnets, trammel nets, and pots. Fishing effort is distributed evenly throughout the year but intensifies in spring and summer, targeting cephalopods, flatfish, and small pelagics depending on the

season. Traditional lagoon fishing techniques persist, with around 70 fishers in the Grado-Marano Lagoon using diversified methods including trammel nets, traps, hand-operated shovels, and cane barriers ("grasiui") for short-range fishing. A particular seasonal feature is the use of traps for cuttlefish in spring and mantis shrimp traps from spring to autumn.

- **Veneto (Caorle and Chioggia):**

The Veneto coast hosts a diversified small-scale fishing sector, particularly around Caorle and Chioggia. Vessels typically range from 4.3 to 11.95 meters in length, with gross tonnages between 1 and 11 tons. Fishing takes place within 0.1 to 3 nautical miles from the shore and is conducted by vessels with 1 to 2 crew members. Artisanal vessels employ four main techniques across different seasons: gillnets, trammel nets, pots, and basket traps. Gillnets are used mainly from May to June and from September to November to target species such as *Solea solea*, *Squilla mantis*, and *Chelidonichthys lucerna*. Trammel nets, used in winter months (January–March, November–December), primarily target flatfish like *Scophthalmus maximus* and *Platichthys flesus*. Pots are deployed from April to July for cuttlefish (*Sepia officinalis*), while basket traps are used from July to October for mantis shrimp (*Squilla mantis*), with particularly high selectivity and low by-catch.

- **Sicily (Gulf of Patti):**

The Gulf of Patti, extending approximately 60 kilometers along the northeastern coast of Sicily, supports a fleet of small vessels (<12 meters), predominantly using gillnets, longlines, pots, and handlines. Fishing is highly seasonal, adapting gear types and target species throughout the year.

- **Spring and Summer:** Drifting longlines for migratory pelagic species (e.g., swordfish *Xiphias gladius*, albacore *Thunnus alalunga*), handlines for squid (*Loligo vulgaris*), and pots for cuttlefish and shrimp.
- **Autumn:** Purse seines and beach seines for dolphinfish (*Coryphaena hippurus*) and small schooling pelagics (e.g., picarel, bogue).
- **Winter:** Fixed longlines for bottom-dwelling species (e.g., European hake *Merluccius merluccius*, scabbardfish *Lepidopus caudatus*) and gillnets for red mullet (*Mullus barbatus*).
- **Year-round:** Trammel nets deployed for a wide range of demersal species, adapting to seasonal shifts in species abundance.

Croatia

The Croatian case study included two distinct pilots: the Velebit Channel and the Vis Archipelago.

- **Velebit Channel**

In 2023, the Velebit Channel hosted 301 registered fishers, of whom 225 (74.75%) operated under the SSF definition. With an average of 1.5 employees per vessel, the SSF sector employed 338 people and accounted for a total of 17,377 fishing days, with vessels active on average 51.4 days per year.

Landings totaled 105.8 tonnes, ranging from 4.75 tonnes in January (limited by poor weather) to 12.6 tonnes in December. A diverse gear portfolio was recorded, with 15 types in use. The most common were gillnets (GNS, 32.4% of fishing days), pots/traps (FPO, 24.6%), and harpoons (HAR, 14.6%), used primarily to target European hake (*Merluccius merluccius*), Norway lobster (*Nephrops norvegicus*), and common octopus (*Octopus vulgaris*).

- **Vis Archipelago**

Within Sub-Zone C4 of Fishing Zone C, 375 fishers were active in 2023, of whom 100 (26.67%) were engaged in SSF, employing 150 people. SSF vessels recorded 6,886 fishing days, averaging 68.9 days per vessel, though activity ranged widely (from 1 to 1,266 days per vessel). Total landings reached 61.9 tonnes, with strong seasonality: a peak in April (11.5 tonnes) and a low in November (282 kg).

The Vis fleet targeted over 68 species, with key landings including European hake (*Merluccius merluccius*), tub gurnard (*Trigla lucerna*), and large-scaled scorpionfish (*Scorpaena scrofa*). Fishers used 11 gear types, most frequently gillnets (GNS, 37.2%), set longlines (LLS, 27.4%), and handlines/pole-lines (LHP, 12.7%). Dominant gear-species combinations included LLS for hake and gurnard, and GNS for scorpionfish.

Türkiye (Mordoğan – Gulf of Izmir)

The Mordoğan fleet comprises a diverse range of small vessels (5–12 meters), using gillnets, longlines, trammel nets, and, in some cases, small trawls. Fishing strategies are seasonally adapted to the availability of both demersal and pelagic species, with artisanal techniques predominant despite the presence of some mechanization.

Tunisia (Gulf of Gabes)

Fishing activities in the Gulf of Gabes are primarily carried out by very small vessels powered by outboard gasoline engines. Fishers employ a combination of passive gears, including trammel nets, gillnets, shrimp nets, and crab pots, with seasonal variations in gear use like those observed in other Mediterranean small-scale fisheries. The fleet is characterized by artisanal, labor-intensive practices closely tied to traditional ecological knowledge.

2.2 DATA COLLECTION PROTOCOL

The data collection followed a standardized methodology adapted from (5) and similar approaches developed for small-scale fisheries assessment (2).

- **Fleet Characterization:** For each site, fleet composition, vessel size, engine type, and primary gear types were recorded.
- **Questionnaire Surveys:** Detailed interviews were conducted with a representative sample of fishers (ideally 10% of the fleet at each site) to collect information on fuel consumption per trip, fishing effort (days at sea), gear types used, catch data (species, quantity and type), and seasonal variations.
- **Vessel Tracking:** At selected sites (Caorle, Chioggia, Patti, Velebit Channel, Vis Archipelago), a subset of vessels was equipped with GPS trackers to validate reported data on trip distances, speeds, and fishing activity duration.

2.3 EMISSION ESTIMATION METHODOLOGY

CO₂ emissions were estimated using the basic method Tier 1 (5,10–12) based on the following equation:

$$CO_2emissions = FC \times EF$$

where *FC* is fuel consumption (in liters), and *EF* is the emission factor (kg CO₂ per liter of fuel).

The emission factors applied were:

- **Diesel:** 2.860 kg CO₂ per liter (12)
- **Gasoline:** 2.324 kg CO₂ per liter (13)

Fuel consumption was estimated using two complementary approaches:

- **Questionnaire Surveys:** Fishers were asked to provide information on their average fuel consumption per fishing trip and the number of fishing trips per month. The questionnaire covered 1 vessel in Friuli Venezia Giulia, 10 vessels in

Veneto, 11 vessels in Sicily, 4 vessels in Croatia (2 in Vis and 2 in Velebit), 29 vessels in Türkiye, and 102 vessels in Tunisia.

- **GPS Tracker Validation:** A subset of vessels was equipped with GPS trackers to monitor real trip distances, durations, and speeds. GPS tracking was conducted on 10 vessels in Veneto, 1 vessel in Sicily, 4 vessels in the Velebit Channel, and 3 vessels in the Vis Archipelago.

Data from GPS-tracked vessels were used to independently estimate fuel consumption, assuming average fuel efficiencies per engine power class based on literature values (2). This cross-validation allowed for checking the consistency and reliability of questionnaire-based estimates.

The GPS devices record both the location and movement of a vessel throughout a fishing trip. To distinguish between periods when the vessel is stationary (e.g., during net placement) and when it is in motion (fuel consumption), the GPS data is used to differentiate between "stationary" and "moving" activities. Only the periods during which the vessel is moving are considered for fuel consumption calculations.

GPS devices provide data on travel distance, time, and speed, which are then used in the following formula to estimate fuel consumption based on engine power and speed (14).

$$FC = a \times P_{max} \times \frac{S}{d} \times t \times 0.001$$

Where:

a = average coefficient

P_{max} = maximum engine power (kW)

S = specific fuel consumption

d = density of fuel (0.86 kg/l for diesel and 0.76 kg/l for gasoline)

t = hours of navigation.

The average coefficient, representing the proportion of maximum engine power effectively used during operation, was set at 0.75 (14). As fuel consumption in SSF vessels is mainly associated with navigation, a specific fuel consumption value of 150.4 g/kW/h was adopted (15). For each vessel, maximum engine power (P_{max}) was obtained from the European Community Fishing Fleet Register. Fuel densities were derived from applicable international standards (16,17).

RESULTS

3.1 EMISSION ESTIMATES BASED ON GEOSPATIAL TRACKING

Among the vessels participating in the project, 17 were monitored in their fishing trips by using geospatial tracker data. In detail, 10 tracked vessels belong to Caorle and Chioggia fisheries, 4 to Velebit fishery, and 3 to Vis fishery. The fuel consumption of the investigated vessels was estimated using the tracked distance as an input for the FC equation. Table 1 shows the results per each vessel unit. The average daily fuel consumption of 37.93 ± 4.34 l and an average daily CO₂ emission of 108.04 ± 12.78 kg was estimated for the 10 vessels from the Caorle/Chioggia pilot. For Croatia, in the Velebit site, the average daily consumption was 38.75 ± 15.62 l, and the CO₂ emission amounted to 89.35 ± 12.78 kg; in the Vis site, the fuel consumed was on average 129.78 ± 74.93 l per day, producing 371.18 ± 214.30 kg of CO₂.

Table 1. Emission results from the sampled vessels, estimated based on GPS-trackers data, in terms of average daily fuel consumptions (FC, expressed in l/day) and related CO₂ emissions (expressed in kg/day)

Caorle/Chioggi a	FC (l/day)	CO ₂ (kg/day)
Vessel 1	44.3	126.6
Vessel 2	25.7	73.6
Vessel 3	37.1	106.0
Vessel 4	31.3	89.5
Vessel 5	49.3	141.0
Vessel 6	47.5	135.9
Vessel 7	45.1	128.9
Vessel 8	8.5	19.7
Vessel 9	55.7	159.4
Vessel 10	34.8	99.6
Velebit Channel		
Vessel 1	12.0	34.2
Vessel 2	16.3	46.5
Vessel 3	50.7	144.9
Vessel 4	78.3	224.0
Vis Archipelago		
Vessel 1	64.9	185.7
Vessel 2	60.6	173.3
Vessel 3	287.5	822.3

3.2 GENERALIZATION OF EMISSION ESTIMATES BASED ON QUESTIONNAIRES

The number of vessels involved with the questionnaire campaign in each pilot varied significantly among sites, from a single vessel in Marano Lagunare (Italy) to over one hundred vessels surveyed in the Gulf of Gabes (Tunisia).

Mean daily fuel consumption declared per vessel ranged from 8.9 kg/day in the Gulf of Gabes to 138.7 kg/day in the Vis Archipelago (Croatia). Correspondingly, mean GHG emissions per vessel per day ranged from 20.6 kg CO₂/day in Tunisia to 396.7 kg CO₂/day in Vis.

In Italian pilot sites, vessels from Caorle and Chioggia exhibited the highest mean daily fuel consumption (85 kg/day) and emissions (241 kg CO₂/day), followed closely by vessels from Patti, Sicily (77 kg/day and 223 kg CO₂/day). Marano Lagunare vessels had much lower daily fuel consumption (21 kg/day) and emissions (48 kg CO₂/day).

In Croatia, emissions varied widely between the Velebit Channel (42 kg CO₂/day) and the Vis Archipelago (396.7 kg CO₂/day).

The Turkish pilot site of Mordoğan showed moderate mean values (12.7 kg/day of fuel consumption and 29.6 kg CO₂/day emissions), comparable to the artisanal fleet of the Gulf of Gabes in Tunisia (Table 2).

Table 2. Summary of the results from the vessels participating via questionnaires.

Country	Pilot Site	Nr. Vessels involved	Mean fuel consumption (kg/day)	Mean GHG emissions (kg CO ₂ /day)
Italy	Marano Lag.	1	21	48
Italy	Caorle/Chioggia	10	85	241
Italy	Patti	11	77	223
Croatia	Velebit Ch.	2	16	42
Croatia	Vis Archipelago	2	139	397
Turkey	Mordoğan	29	13	30
Tunisia	Gulf of Gabes	102	9	21

3.3 SEASONAL FLEET EMISSIONS

Total annual GHG emissions varied widely across pilot sites (Table 3), reflecting differences in fleet size, fishing effort, and seasonal targeting strategies. The highest total annual emissions were observed in Caorle and Chioggia (Italy), with over 8,671 tonnes of

CO₂, peaking in autumn (3,711 t), followed by summer (2,151 t) and spring (1,622 t).

In Patti (Sicily), emissions were concentrated in spring (1,189 t) and summer (572 t), with much lower activity in autumn (288 t) and especially winter (24 t). This strong seasonal pattern is consistent with the operation of longlines and handlines targeting pelagic species during warmer months.

Croatian sites showed high total emissions, particularly in Vis Archipelago, which reported 4,500 tonnes of CO₂, with summer (2,146 t) and autumn (1,390 t) accounting for the majority of the total. Velebit Channel followed with 3,092 tonnes, displaying a similar seasonal profile, with peaks in summer (1,661 t) and autumn (846 t). Spring and winter contributed less, although spring emissions in Velebit (511 t) remained relevant.

The Gulf of Gabes in Tunisia showed a nearly uniform seasonal distribution of emissions, with around 156 tonnes per season and a slightly lower value in winter (125 t). This reflects the year-round, low-intensity fishing activity typical of the Tunisian SSF sector.

In Mordoğan (Türkiye), the total emissions were very low, totaling just 3 tonnes, with emissions recorded only in spring (2 t) and summer (1 t). It must be noted that no data were gathered for Autumn and Winter.

No seasonal emission estimates were available for Marano Lagunare, as only one vessel was surveyed, and extrapolation was not possible.

Table 3. Estimated seasonal and total annual CO₂ emissions (tonnes) for the small-scale fishing fleet at each pilot site.

Country	Pilot Site	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter	Total
Italy	Marano Lagunare	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Italy	Caorle - Chioggia	1622	2151	3711	1187	8671
Italy	Patti	1189	572	288	24	2073
Croatia	Velebit Channel	511	1661	846	74	3092
Croatia	Vis Archipelago	483	2146	1390	481	4500
Turkey	Mordoğan	2	1	NA	NA	3
Tunisia	Gulf of Gabes	156	156	156	125	593

3.4 EMISSION INTENSITY

Emission intensity, expressed as kilograms of CO₂ per kilogram of landings and per euro of landing value, showed substantial variation across sites, seasons, and target species (Figure 2-8; Appendix A Tables A1-A5). Values derived from questionnaire data confirmed heterogeneous carbon efficiency among the small-scale fishing fleets involved.

Across sites, Tunisia reported the highest average emission intensity per kilogram of landings, consistently above 60 kg CO₂/kg throughout the year. Seasonal variability was limited. On the species level, high emission values were recorded in Tunisia for *Octopus*

sp., *Solea solea*, and *Dicentrarchus labrax*, while species such as *Sardina pilchardus* and *Portunus segnis* showed markedly lower values (Figure 3).

Croatian sites, including both Vis and Velebit, displayed lower average emission intensities, generally below 10 kg CO₂/kg. Seasonal variation was moderate, and most species fell within a relatively narrow range of values (Figure 4). Higher intensities were associated with species such as *Nephrops norvegicus* and *Loligo vulgaris*.

In Mordoğan (Türkiye), average intensities per kilogram ranged between 20 and 40 kg CO₂/kg, with high ranges observed across species (Figure 5). Emission intensity per euro also displayed considerable variability, influenced by species-specific market values.

Veneto presented intermediate values of emission intensity, showing elevated kg CO₂/kg ratios for *Chelidonichthys lucerna*, *Squilla mantis*, and *Callinectes sapidus* (Figure 6). Seasonal variability was more evident compared to other sites.

Patti (Sicily) exhibited the widest spread in both indicators. While most species remained under 100 kg CO₂/kg, a few taxa exceeded 500 kg CO₂/kg, reaching over 1,000 kg CO₂/kg in rare cases (Figure 7). Emission intensity per euro followed a similar trend, with most values clustered in the lower range but occasional spikes.

Figure 2. Seasonal emission intensity expressed as kg CO₂ per kg of landing and kg CO₂ per € of landing, for all the involved sites.

Figure 3. Average emission intensity expressed as kg CO₂ per kg of landing and kg CO₂ per € of landing, for Veneto (Italy). Vertical bars represent standard deviation.

Figure 4. Average emission intensity expressed as kg CO₂ per kg of landing and kg CO₂ per € of landing for Patti (Italy). Vertical bars represent standard deviation.

Figure 5. Emission intensity expressed as kg CO₂ per kg of landing and kg CO₂ per € of landing, for Vis (Croatia). Vertical bars represent standard deviation.

Figure 6. Emission intensity expressed as kg CO₂ per kg of landing and kg CO₂ per € of landing, for Velebit (Croatia). Vertical bars represent standard deviation.

Figure 7. Emission intensity expressed as kg CO₂ per kg of landing and kg CO₂ per € of landing, for Mordoğan (Türkiye). Vertical bars represent standard deviation.

Figure 8. Emission intensity expressed as kg CO₂ per kg of landing and kg CO₂ per € of landing, for the Gulf of Gabes (Tunisia). Economic data were lacking in this site.

DISCUSSION

This report represents the first coordinated effort to compare GHG emissions from Small-Scale Fisheries across a representative set of Mediterranean pilot sites.

The inventory confirms the high variability in carbon emissions across Mediterranean SSF, influenced by vessel characteristics, gear types, seasonal activity, and target species. Turkish and Tunisian fisheries showed lower daily fuel consumption and emissions compared to their Italian and Croatian counterparts – an expected result, considering the widespread use of small petrol-powered outboard vessels in the former, versus larger inboard diesel-powered boats (although still within the 12 m LOA limit) in the latter.

Emission intensities ranged from under 10 kg CO₂/kg in Croatian sites to over 60 kg CO₂/kg in Tunisia, highlighting both the structural diversity of the sector and the need for tailored mitigation strategies (18,19). Compared to the Adriatic SSF analysed by Cavraro et al. (5), which reported average intensities of 7.01 kg CO₂/kg and 2.08 kg CO₂/€, several pilot sites in this report displayed less favourable values – particularly where low-value landings or inefficient gear-fuel combinations prevail. However, the broader spatial and temporal scope of this study, encompassing North African and Eastern Mediterranean contexts, offers a more complete picture of the challenges and potential pathways for emission reductions.

Despite the diverse socio-ecological contexts in which the fleets operate, some common patterns emerge. A consistent trend across sites suggests that main commercial target species tend to be associated with lower emission intensities. This supports the idea that selectivity and targeting efficiency – core strengths of artisanal fishing – can translate into reduced carbon footprints (5,19). However, exceptions exist. For instance, fishing techniques targeting *Mustelus mustelus* in Veneto showed unusually high emission intensities, likely due to long distances traveled and disproportionate fuel use relative to the landed value. These outliers may warrant further attention from a management perspective.

Other differences are evident when examining daily fuel consumption. Among Adriatic fleets, vessels in Chioggia and Caorle reported daily averages around 85 l, comparable to Velebit Channel (38.8 l/day), while vessels from the Vis Archipelago averaged over 129 l/day – more than double. This disparity is explained by the geographic and operational context: Vis is a remote island exposed to the open sea, and fishers must travel long distances – sometimes as far as Mljet or Montenegro – to reach fishing grounds. Gear types also differ: longlines, more fuel-intensive and spatially extensive, are

widely used in Vis, while gillnets and traps are dominant in the Velebit fleet. Fishing trips in Vis often last several days or weeks, whereas single-day outings are typical in Velebit. Additionally, winter and spring weather conditions frequently prevent Vis fishers from going to sea, leading to fewer total fishing days over the year.

The comparison between questionnaire-based estimates and GPS-based data revealed discrepancies, particularly in Italy, where fuel use estimated from engine specifications was systematically lower – about half – than values self-reported by fishers. This aligns with findings from Cavraro et al. (2023) and likely reflects underreported engine upgrades or overreported fuel use for regulatory or economic reasons. Conversely, GPS-based estimates in Croatia aligned well with survey data in Velebit and even exceeded them in Vis, likely due to the small sample size of questionnaire respondents there.

Despite the strengths of this investigation, several limitations must be acknowledged. The Marano Lagunare dataset was based on a single fisher and is not representative of Friuli Venezia Giulia. In Türkiye, data were collected only in spring and summer, and while participation was high, most fishers contributed only one or two surveys, limiting robustness. In Tunisia, data were derived from administrative sources rather than direct questionnaires, offering full coverage but relying on coarse estimates of fishing effort, which limits cross-site comparability.

Future efforts should explore more effective methods of engagement with fishers to improve data representativeness and temporal consistency, while also leveraging the empirical knowledge of local fishing communities (20,21).

These findings confirm that mitigating emissions in SSF requires context-specific approaches. While the SSF sector is broadly recognised for its low environmental impact and cultural value (Cavraro et al., 2023), its internal variability in terms of gear, effort, and species composition requires flexible and targeted strategies. Policymaking should prioritize standardized data collection, promote voluntary reporting tools, and consider species-level emission intensities as criteria for management and certification schemes. Provided that these metrics are based on reliable and transparent estimates – ideally measured rather than inferred – CO₂ intensity labelling could inform consumers and reshape demand toward more sustainable seafood choices (3,22).

Importantly, further harmonization of data collection methods across the Mediterranean is needed. The use of geospatial tracking, combined with validated socio-economic surveys, offers a solid foundation for building regional emission baselines. This is especially relevant in light of the new EU Fisheries Control Regulation, which will make real-time vessel tracking mandatory for SSF, either via VMS systems or dedicated mobile apps. This regulatory shift aims to enhance compliance, monitoring, and traceability, and

could provide a unique opportunity to align GHG monitoring with broader governance and sustainability objectives (19,23).

Looking ahead, investments in low-emission technologies, seasonally adaptive fishing strategies, and fisher-led co-management could prove to be the most effective way to reduce GHG emissions in SSF while safeguarding their social and economic viability.

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